

Improvement of ENDF/B-VIII.1 Library Generation and Correction System for Lattice Calculation of HTGR System

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the generation of a 190-group cross section library based on ENDF/B-VIII.1 is performed for high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR) system. Multi-group cross section libraries for neutron transport lattice codes can be produced by KAERI library generation system. For the application of the latest evaluated nuclear data, ENDF/B-VIII.1, improvement of KAERI multi-group library generation system is performed. Not only neutron cross section data, but also fission product yield, decay and photo-atomic interaction data provided from ENDF/B-VIII.1, are applied for the library generation. After that, library correction is performed based on group-wise correction factor method. McCARD continuous energy Monte-Carlo code calculation is performed for MHTGR-350 single compact problem to provide reference solution for library correction. Library generation and correction system is validated by comparing reactivity errors between McCARD and DeCART2D. RMS error of reactivity reduced up to 21 pcm. Also, comparison of MHTGR-350 single fuel block and 2D core benchmark analysis results calculated by McCARD and DeCART2D using corrected libraries are included in this study. The minimum RMS error of reactivity calculated as 21 pcm in FB35 fuel block problem. Although the RMS error of FB30 fuel block and 2D core problems arose compared to FB35 fuel block results, it is shown that library correction system can be applied to HTGR systems.

Keywords: Multi-group cross section, Library generation and correction system, ENDF/B-VIII.1, MHTGR-350 benchmark.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGR) possess core characteristics distinct from those of Light Water Reactor (LWR), including double heterogeneity caused by tri-structural isotropic (TRISO) fuel particles, high operating temperatures, and a hexagonal core configuration, among others. To consider these distinctive characteristics of HTGR systems, Korea Atomic Energy Research Institute (KAERI) developed DeCART2D/CAPP code system by adopting a two-step core analysis procedure [1-2]. DeCART2D code which uses pre-generated multi-group cross section library performs neutron transport calculations and generates Homogenized Group Constant (HGC) data. The generated HGC data are then utilized in CAPP code for whole core diffusion calculation. Consequently, while the accuracy of each code contributes to the overall whole core analysis results, the accuracy of the multi-group cross-section library plays a decisive role. Thus, high-fidelity multi-group cross section library is essential for accurate HTGR core design.

Multi-group cross section library used in DeCART2D code can be generated by KAERI library generation system [3]. This system produces multi-group cross sections from ENDF/B data and performs resonance treatment based on the subgroup method. However, in these processes, the approximation that utilizes typical neutron spectrum induces the errors compared to the actual reactor core parameters. In order to minimize these errors, the automatic library correction system based on

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correction factor using the Monte-Carlo calculation result was developed by Kim and Park. [4]. Although this system has been validated to LWR system including APR-1400, SMART and NEA MOX benchmark problems, validation for HTGR systems has not yet been conducted. A 190-group cross section library is required for HTGR transport analysis, enabling the consideration of wide temperature ranges and double heterogeneity due to varying packing fractions. In this study, the generation of 190 group cross section library for HTGR system is performed using library generation and correction system. Also, the validation of the library generated for HTGR system is conducted using MHTGR-350 benchmark problem [5].

Meanwhile, KAERI library generation system utilizes ENDF/B format evaluated nuclear data files. The system utilizes not only neutron cross section data, but fission product yield decay, photo-atomic interaction data are used in this system. Most of existing multi-group library is based on ENDF/B-VII.1, since the conventional library generation system is partially incompatible with the ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries due to data diversification and changes in data format. However, ENDF/B-VIII.1 provides not only the latest evaluated nuclear data, but also various thermal scattering data for graphite moderators, enabling more precise HTGR core analysis. Consequently, improvement of library generation system to apply ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 is also conducted in this study.

2. MULTI-GROUP LIBRARY GENERATION FOR HTGR SYSTEM

2.1. Improvement of KAERI Library Generation System

Figure 1 represents the flow of conventional KAERI library generation system. The ANJOYG and ANJOY code generate NJOY inputs for all user-defined nuclides and batch script for automatic NJOY execution. The NJOY outputs calculated by GAMINR, GROUPT, BROADR module are then processed by the GREDITG, GREDIT and MERIT, respectively. GREDITG and GREDIT generate multi-group cross section files as a function of temperatures and background cross sections. Simultaneously, MERIT produces resonance integral table (RIT) by solving neutron slowing-down equation for resonant nuclides. Subsequently, SUBDATA produces subgroup parameters using RIT. Consequently, LIBGEN produces a multi-group cross section library using cross section files produced by GREDIT and GREDITG and RIT and subgroup parameters produced by MERIT and SUBDATA. Furthermore, the fission product yield, decay data from the ENDF file are processed in LIBGEN to produce multi-group cross section library.

Figure 1. Conventional KAERI library generation system

Within this code system, ANJOY and LIBGEN are directly affected by the format changes of ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1. Following the update of the NJOY version to NJOY2016 [6] as part of the ENDF/B version update, the ANJOY code is modified to produce proper NJOY inputs. The major improvement is focused on the processing of thermal scattering data. ENDF/B-VIII.1 provides 114 thermal scattering data, while only 21 thermal scattering data are provided by ENDF/B-VII.1. The ANJOY code is modified to produce NJOY input to handle all thermal scattering data provided in ENDF/B-VIII.1.

The LIBGEN code is also modified to process ENDF/B-VIII.1. The LIBGEN code requires scattering radius from ENDF data to calculate potential scattering cross section. The scattering radius has been provided in a unified format in ENDF/B-VII.1 or previous version. However, ENDF/B-VIII.1 provides thermal scattering data in various data formats to give specified scattering radius. In this regard, LIBGEN is modified to find and read scattering radius from ENDF/B format data. Modifications for extensibility are also conducted. In the previous version of the LIBGEN code, the FORTRAN format for reading ENDF/B data varied depending on the type of data being processed. In order to ensure compatibility with future ENDF version updates, the formats are unified to the "E11.0" FORTRAN format specified in the ENDF format manual.

2.2. Library Correction Methodology

In the KAERI library generation system, an approximation is employed that utilizes the typical neutron spectrum for group collapsing. Thus, the library initially generated by the KAERI library generation system contains errors compared to reactor design parameters. In this regard, Kim and Park. [4] developed efficient library correction system that can be integrated into the KAERI library generation system. Figure 2 represents the multi-group library generation system includes library correction system.

Figure 2. Multi-group library generation includes library correction system

In this library correction system, group-wise correction factors are calculated for multi-group cross section correction. These factors can be calculated by using the group-wise reaction rate calculated by Monte-Carlo code and transport lattice code as represented in equation [1].

$$f_{x,g,i}(T) = \frac{\sigma_{x,g,i}^{MC} \cdot \phi_g^{MC}(T)}{\sigma_{x,g,i}^{Lattice} \cdot \phi_g^{Lattice}(T)} \quad (1)$$

where $f_{x,g,i}(T)$ represents the correction factor as a function of temperature T , according to the reaction type x , energy group g , and nuclide index i . $\sigma_{x,g,i}^{MC}$ and ϕ_g^{MC} represent the microscopic cross section and flux calculated by the Monte-Carlo code while $\sigma_{x,g,i}^{Lattice}$ and $\phi_g^{Lattice}$ are calculated by the transport lattice code.

The CORRA code produces the group-wise correction factor for user-defined nuclides and neutron reactions. After that, the CORRXS and CORRIT produce corrected multi-group neutron cross section

data and RIT. This correction procedure is performed through multiple rounds of iteration to ensure the convergence of correction factors. Consequently, the high-fidelity Monte-Carlo reaction rate can be reproduced in transport lattice calculation. In order to perform library correction, reference McCARD solution should be prepared and DeCART2D input for the coincident problem is required.

2.3. Library Generation Procedure

For 190 group cross section library generation, not only neutron cross section data, but also decay, fission product yield and photo-atomic interaction data provided by ENDF/B-VIII.1 are used in this study. The temperature grids for NJOY calculation are set to 300 K, 700 K, 1000K, 1200 K, 1600 K and 2000 K, considering HTGR operation condition. In addition, for the RIT production by MERIT code, the slowing-down equation for homogeneous fuel pin cell problem consists of uranium, silicon and carbon is solved in order to consider the typical HTGR fuel configuration. The uncorrected library which is produced directly by the KAERI library generation system is then corrected by library correction system.

In this study, the OECD/NEA MHTGR-350 benchmark based on the General Atomics design are modeled for library correction and benchmark analysis. For library correction, MHTGR-350 single compact problem is modeled by McCARD to provide reference reaction rate. Total 10 iteration rounds of library correction are performed and each transport calculation results are compared with McCARD result to validate library correction system in HTGR system. MHTGR-350 fuel block and 2D core benchmark analysis are also performed to validate the generated library. In MHTGR-350 benchmark problem, standard fuel block consists of 210 fuel compacts and reserved shut-down control (RSC) fuel block. However, for the simplification RSC fuel block is replaced to the fuel block consist of 210 fuel compacts with 30% of packing fraction. In this perspective, two different fuel block models compose the benchmark problem. FB35 indicates the fuel block problem consists of the fuel compact with 35% of packing fraction. Similarly, FB30 denotes the corresponding configuration with a 30% of packing fraction.

Figure 3. Fuel block and 2D core configurations of MHTGR-350 benchmark

For the validation of the library correction system for HTGR applications, MHTGR-350 single compact problem is used as a reference model. The Monte-Carlo calculation results are provided by the McCARD and DeCART2D is used for transport lattice calculation. The correction is performed for a total of 10 rounds and Figure 4 and Table I represent the reactivity error and root mean square (RMS) error during correction, respectively. UCR indicates the uncorrected library and the numbers with R index represent the correction rounds. The RMS error of reactivity reduced to 21 pcm in 10 rounds corrected library.

Table II represents RMS errors of reaction rate calculated by DeCART2D using uncorrected library and 10 round corrected library, compared to McCARD reference reaction rate. RMS error of the fission reaction rate of ^{238}U shows maximum 4.17%. Large contribution of (n,2n) and (n,3n) reaction in ^{238}U absorption reaction induce these errors since (n,2n) and (n,3n) is not corrected in the library correction system. However, RMS error of fission reaction rate of ^{238}U , fission and absorption reaction rate of ^{235}U show less than 0.2%.

Figure 4. Reactivity error of each correction rounds in single compact problem

Table I. RMS error of each correction rounds in single compact problem

Correction rounds	UCR	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
RMS error (pcm)	414	232	89	51	64	29	28	25	27	22	21

Table II. RMS error of group-wise reaction rate

Correction rounds		RMS errors (%)					
		300 K	700 K	1000 K	1200 K	1600 K	2000 K
Absorption reaction rate of ^{235}U	UCR	218.65	161.86	184.23	146.60	120.24	101.09
	R10	0.48	0.41	0.35	0.43	0.41	0.40
Fission reaction rate of ^{235}U	UCR	218.64	161.85	184.21	146.58	120.21	101.07
	R10	0.19	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
Absorption reaction rate of ^{238}U	UCR	220.21	162.91	185.35	147.45	120.89	101.60
	R10	3.76	4.05	3.78	4.17	4.10	4.10
Fission reaction rate of ^{238}U	UCR	220.88	163.78	186.11	148.40	122.06	103.00
	R10	0.19	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01

3. BENCHMARK ANALYSIS RESULT

3.1. MHTGR-350 Single Fuel Block Benchmark

Figure 5-6 and Table III represent the reactivity errors and RMS errors for the MHTGR-350 FB35 and FB30 benchmark analyses. RMS error in reactivity reaches a minimum of 21 pcm for FB35 problem which shows a similar result compared to single compact problem. However, the library correction is performed with fuel compact problem which has 35 % of packing fraction. In this regard, the RMS error in reactivity reaches a minimum of 68 pcm in the FB30 problem.

Figure 5. Reactivity error of MHTGR-350 FB35 benchmark analysis

Figure 6. Reactivity error of MHTGR-350 FB30 benchmark analysis

Table III. RMS error of MHTGR-350 FB35 and FB30 benchmark analysis

Correction rounds	UCR	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
RMS error (pcm)	FB35	669	305	139	131	88	40	31	23	21	26
	FB30	622	257	112	127	115	74	68	74	76	92

3.2. MHTGR-350 2D Core Benchmark

Figure 7 and Table IV represent the reactivity errors and RMS errors for MHTGR-350 2D core benchmark analysis. As shown in FB30 benchmark analysis results, DeCART2D calculation results overestimate the reactivity in the 2D core problem. The minimum RMS error occurs in 2 round corrected library as 91 pcm, however, the errors increase up to 228 pcm. Since only ^{235}U and ^{238}U are corrected in this study, it is estimated that the uncorrected cross section of carbon affects this result. Also, the amount of graphite is much higher compared to fuel loading than the fuel block problem, large reactivity errors occur in this result.

The cross sections of carbon have no resonances in absorption and fission reactions, however, it can be estimated that scattering cross section or scattering matrix affects the reactor core parameters as graphite plays a role as moderator. Also, it should be considered that the error induced by thermal scattering cross section.

Figure 7. Reactivity error of MHTGR-350 2D core benchmark analysis

Table IV. RMS error of MHTGR-350 2D core benchmark analysis

Correction rounds	UCR	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	R9	R10
RMS error (pcm)	425	136	91	114	178	174	181	194	204	217	228

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a 190-group cross section library for HTGR systems based on ENDF/B-VIII.1 evaluated data is generated using improved library generation and correction system. The improvement of KAERI library generation system is conducted to apply neutron cross section, fission yield, decay and photo-atomic interaction data from ENDF/B-VIII.1. The generation of uncorrected library is performed using improve library generation system while considering the characteristics of HTGR systems. Subsequently, the uncorrected library generated is then corrected for MHTGR-350 single compact problem. For the validation of improved library generation and correction system, the comparison of reactivity error from McCARD and DeCART2D calculation for MHTGR-350 benchmark is performed.

The RMS error of MHTGR-350 single compact problem, which is utilized for library correction, shows minimum 21 pcm. MHTGR-350 single block and 2D core benchmark analyses are also performed using generated libraries. Although relatively large errors arose for FB30 and 2D core problems compared to FB35 problem, it is shown that the library correction system can efficiently reduce the reactivity errors in HTGR systems.

Since the library correction system contains the capability for scattering matrix correction, library correction includes scattering cross section of carbon and thermal scattering cross section of graphite will be performed to reduce the remaining reactivity error in FB35 and 2D core problems as the next works. Furthermore, optimization of library correction using other HTGR systems will be performed for generally applicable multi-group cross section library for HTGR systems.

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